

SHOOT MULTIPLICATION OF *CURCUMA SUMATRANA* MODIFIED MURASHIGE AND SKOOG WITH THE ADDITION OF THIDIAZURON GROWTH REGULATOR

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Based on previous research on the use of in vitro culture methods for shoot growth in several plants has provided significant understanding. The main focus of these studies on the treatment with the addition of growth regulator, especially is Thidiazuron. The discovery of a new compound known as Thidiazuron (TDZ) opened up opportunities for successful shoot formation in in vitro culture (Alatar, 2015). Thidiazuron (TDZ) is a cytokinin that stimulates shoot multiplication in low concentrations (Restanto et al., 2018). Cytokinin hormones are synthesized at the root tip and translocated through the xylem vessels. This hormone functions to stimulate cell division (Sukowardana et al., 2017). On the other hand, there is a lack of information on the effectiveness of TDZ addition in herbaceous plants, especially in the Zingiberaceae family. Zingiberaceae is one of the plant families commonly used as traditional medicine. The rhizome of the zingiberaceae family is a commonly utilized part of this plant because it contains secondary metabolites (Elfahmi et al., 2014). The rhizome will experience dormancy during the dry season, so planting of this plant is usually done during the rainy season (Samanhudi et al., 2021). In order to meet the need for seeds to replace rhizomes, the procurement of seeds can be done in vitro. With the title "Multiplication of *Curcuma Sumatrana* Shoots Modified Murashige and Skoog with the Addition of Thidiazuron Growth Regulator", this study aims to fill the existing knowledge gap by evaluating the effect of adding Thidiazuron (TDZ) in the early stages of *Curcuma Sumatrana* shoot growth through in vitro culture methods. Plant tissue culture plays an important role as an alternative in producing indispensable secondary metabolites from plants (Karuppusamy, 2009). *Curcuma sumatrana* is a curcuma species first collected by Dielpenhorst in Pariaman, West Sumatra, Indonesia, described by Miquel in a supplement to "Flora van Nederlandsch Indië" in 1861 (Ardiyani et al., 2011). It is expected that the findings of this study will provide a deeper understanding of the response of *Curcuma Sumatrana* to the TDZ in the culture medium, particularly in terms of shoot growth. This research can make a meaningful contribution to the development of more effective and efficient in vitro culture techniques for herbaceous plant multiplication, as well as expanding the application of TDZ in plant tissue culture.

A number of previous theses have examined the use of in vitro culture for shoot growth in various plants, especially in higher plants. The thesis from Swandra (2012), discusses the effect of Thidiazuron on the multiplication of Andalas buds (*Morus macroura* Miq. var *macroura*), and another thesis discusses the effect of giving some combinations of Thidiazuron (TDZ), Benzyl Amino Purin (BAP) and Naftalen Acetic Acid (NAA) growth regulator on the multiplication of Cinnamon Buds (*Cinnamomum Burmanii* Bl.) in vitro culture (Anischan, 2009), showed that the addition of the Thidiazuron (TDZ) growth regulator and a combination of several other growth regulators significantly increased the height and number of shoots in plants. Likewise, another thesis optimizing in vitro culture medium for shoot growth found that modification of Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium

with the addition of growth hormones can significantly improve shoot growth. Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium is a planting medium that is widely used in tissue culture techniques because it consists of macronutrients, micronutrients, carbon sources, vitamins, and various regulators (Mahfudza et al., 2018). The right combination of basic media and growth regulators will increase cell division activity in plants (Lestari, 2011). One of the commonly used growth regulators is TDZ a cytokinin synthesizer that is good for regenerating several plant species (Guo et al., 2011). However, although there have been previous efforts in studying the shoot growth of various plants through in vitro culture, specific research on the use of TDZ in in vitro culture for shoot growth of herbaceous plants, especially the Zingiberaceae family is still very limited. Therefore, there is a need to fill this knowledge gap by exploring the effects of TDZ on the shoot growth of *Curcuma sumatrana* in the context of in vitro culture, which is the focus of this study.

This research aims to address the knowledge gap identified from previous studies, particularly in the context of the use of the Thidiazuron (TDZ) growth regulator on the growth of shoots of herbaceous plants, such as *Curcuma Sumatrana*, in in vitro culture. From the results of research by Fuziani et al. (2023), the concentration of TDZ 1 ppm is effective in increasing the speed of shoot emergence in Dendrobium Orchid plants. The use of TDZ in Zingiberaceae family plants is found in the research of Murgayanti et al., (2021), TDZ concentration of 1.5 ppm gives better results on the number of new shoots on white temu rhizome plants (*Curcuma zedoria*) and in the research of Kholifah et al., (2022), TDZ 4 ppm gives a better effect on shoot length and TDZ 2 ppm produces the highest number of shoots on Kencur plants (*Kaempferia galanga* L.). The other research from Kartini and Karyanti (2017), TDZ with a concentration of 0.6 mg/L produced the highest number of shoots on Satoimo (*Colocasia esculenta* L. Schott var antiquorum) plants using Murashige and Skoog (MS) media. According to Swandra et al., (2012), the length of shoots decreased with an increase in TDZ concentration and conversely, the number of shoots increased with a decrease in TDZ concentration. Based on the results of the above research, it can be seen that the Thidiazuron (TDZ) growth regulator can stimulate shoot multiplication in low concentrations and can produce dwarf shoots with low quality at high concentrations. Based on the research of Gayatri et al., (2024) the use of Murashige and Skoog (MS) media with the addition of TDZ growth regulator in *Curcuma pseudomontana* plants experienced 100% rooting success and a 92% survival rate after acclimatization. The use of TDZ is an efficient way for in vitro propagation of endangered medicinal plants, such as *Rauvolifera serpentina*, experiencing 100% rooting success and a 90% survival rate after acclimatization (Alatar, 2015).

Based on the results of research by Sari et al., (2013), the percentage of explants that live and produce new shoots on *Tetrastigma rafflesiae* Miq. plants using Murashige and Skoog (MS) media is 100%. As well as research by Yulizar et al., (2014), the percentage of explants that live and produce new shoots on *Curcuma zedoaria* Roscoe plants using Murashige and Skoog (MS) media is 100%. This shows that the MS medium used has been considered to provide sufficient nutrients for the growth of *C. zedoaria* explants which belong to the herbaceous group. The success of in vitro culture is strongly influenced by growth regulators. The growth regulator plays an important role in the process of explant regeneration until it becomes a complete plant. The interaction of the growth regulator in the

culture medium determines the direction of explant development (Pamungkas, 2015). In addition, in-vitro growth regulators can initiate the formation of plant organs. The expected organs in in-vitro development can be buds (Choiri and Suhada, 2019). Through this study, it is hoped to deepen the understanding of the effects of Thidiazuron (TDZ) addition on shoot growth of *Curcuma Sumatrana* and identify optimal conditions for shoot multiplication of this plant. By adapting methodologies that have proven effective from previous studies, such as modification of the culture medium and evaluation of shoot growth parameters, it will be attempted to explore the response of *Curcuma Sumatrana* to TDZ in greater detail. It will also expand the scope of the study by considering variations in TDZ concentration and interactions with other components in the culture medium. Thus, it is hoped that this study will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the use of TDZ in vitro culture for shoot multiplication of *Curcuma Sumatrana*, as well as provide practical guidance for the industry and conservation of herbaceous plants.

Based on research that has been conducted on the use of in vitro culture for shoot growth in various plants, especially focusing on the use of Thidiazuron (TDZ) as a growth regulator, it was found that TDZ has the potential to increase shoot multiplication in vitro culture, especially in herbaceous plants from the Zingiberaceae family such as *Curcuma Sumatrana*. Although many studies have optimized MS culture medium with TDZ addition in other plants, specific research on the Zingiberaceae family is still very limited. Therefore, this study aims to fill the knowledge gap by exploring the effects of TDZ in depth on the shoot growth of *Curcuma Sumatrana*. It is hoped that this study will not only increase the understanding of plant responses to TDZ in culture medium but will also contribute significantly to the development of more effective and efficient in vitro culture techniques for herbaceous plant multiplication. Through the use of proven effective methodologies from previous studies and careful evaluation of shoot growth parameters, it is hoped that optimal conditions can be found to maximize the yield of *Curcuma Sumatrana* shoot multiplication. This will provide valuable practical guidance for the industry as well as conservation efforts of ecologically and culturally important herbaceous plants. I am confident that with this approach, the identified knowledge gaps can be successfully addressed, paving the way for further developments in TDZ application and in vitro culture technology for herbaceous plants, particularly in the Zingiberaceae family.

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